

ISic1636

I.Sicily inscription 1636

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 13043

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Hic iacet beñeñe
2. morie Albina h(onesta) f(emina) qui
3. vixxs(it) an(nos) pl(us) m(inus) LX êt requi
4. evit in pace IIII kal(enda)s feb(ruarias) qui ia
5. cet cu(m) mari(t)o f(e)l(icis) m(emoriae)

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1893 with slight changes based on Orsi's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493921

EDCS 12700064

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.73
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 287 no.37

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